

Blockchain Investor & Advisor

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The blockchain technology has witnessed a significant amount of awareness during 2017, many ICOs has been funded with staggering amount of money. Blockchain must overcome few issues before it can be reasonably adopted by the masses, including transaction processing speed, scalability and software development and deployment costs.

2. Aim

Reduce the costs\complexity of running a blockchain node, while increasing the speed of transaction processing.

3. Material and methods

SegWit2X for Bitcoin which took place at the end of Dec last year and the upcoming Lightning Network.

Moving from Proof of Work to Proof of Stake for Ethereum, followed by Sharding and off-chain transactions

Lightning and PoS have their own challenges and are not yet implemented, but they have a huge promise in accelerating the transaction processing speed

4. Results

Proof of Stake is supposed to double or triple the transaction speed (currently around 15\s), while Sharding can bring it to 5x - 10x

SegWit2X helped to increase the # of transactions from 3-4 trx\s to 7-8 trx\s (without the segregated transactions) and up to 30 trx\s with the segregated transactions. This is mainly due to the increase of block size from 1 MB to 2MB and the ability to fit more transactions within the same space

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5. Conclusions

There is still a very long way to go until either Bitcoin or Ethereum (the two most famous and dominant by market cap) can support mass adoption. Network congestions has already been witnessed many times. However, the development teams are working constantly on improving the scalability issues.

6. Keywords

Blockchain; Bitcoin; Ethereum; Decentralization

Author biography

Richard Shibi Richard Shibi has completed BSc in Computer Science from the university of Hertfordshire in London and currently studying MBA at Imperial Collage business school. He has more than 15 years of experience in the IT industry, mainly in the Telecommunication sector (BSS). Richard has lived and worked in USA, Europe, Afrika and Asia. He has successfully deployed IT projects to the world leading Telecoms including Rogers(Canada), at&t(USA), Mobitel Group (Europe) and many others.

Richard is an investor and influencer in the Blockchain sphere, and he has been working as a blockchain consultant since early 2017